

Understanding Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer Conjecture: Continued Fractions and ABC Conjecture

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Abstract

Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer Conjecture can be understood with uniqueness provided by continued fractions.

1 Introduction

Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture is about getting the number of solutions given in the integer driven equation[1].

2 Extension of Goldbach's theorem

The result of Goldbach's theorem is that any even number can be expressed in form of adding two prime numbers. And for any prime number, every prime number is odd number. So following theorem can be derived:

Theorem 2.1. *Any integer number larger than zero can be expressed in orderly combination of two conditions for sequence a_n and prime number sequence p_n :*

$$a_n, \exists x \begin{cases} \text{is odd} \implies 1 + p_x + p_{x+1} \\ \text{is even} \implies p_x + p_{x+1} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

And for so, any integer number can be generalized into form of continued fractions of prime numbers.

Proof.

$$\forall p_{x+1} = n(n+1)(n+2)p_x + p_k \quad (2)$$

For $\forall p_x$:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{x+1} - p_k &= n(n+1)(n+2)p_x \\ \implies p_x &= \frac{p_{x+1} - p_k}{n(n+1)(n+2)} \\ \implies \frac{1}{p_n} &= \frac{n(n+1)(n+2)}{p_{x+1} - p_k} = \frac{1}{\frac{p_{x+1} - p_k}{n(n+1)(n+2)}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

And with $p_{x+1} - p_k$ can be factorized into even number that multiplies with the other prime number:

$$\frac{1}{p_x} = \frac{1}{\frac{2p_m \cdot l}{n(n+1)(n+2)}} \quad (4)$$

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And $2p_m$ can arbitrarily take any form of another sum of two numbers related to prime number:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{\frac{2p_m \cdot l}{n(n+1)(n+2)}} \implies \frac{1}{\frac{2(n'(n'+1)(n'+2)p_q + p_r) \cdot l}{n(n+1)(n+2)}} \\
& \implies \frac{1}{2l \frac{n'(n'+1)(n'+2)}{n(n+1)(n+2)} p_q + 2l \frac{1}{n(n+1)(n+2)} p_r} \\
& \implies \frac{1}{2l \frac{n'(n'+1)(n'+2)}{n(n+1)(n+2)} p_q + \frac{1}{\frac{n(n+1)(n+2)}{2lp_r}}}
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Note that l is a composite number. With applying $\frac{1}{p_x} = \frac{1}{\frac{2p_m \cdot l}{n(n+1)(n+2)}}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{p_x} &= \frac{1}{2l \frac{n'(n'+1)(n'+2)}{n(n+1)(n+2)} p_q + \frac{1}{\frac{n(n+1)(n+2)}{2lp_r}}} \\
&= \frac{1}{2l \frac{n'(n'+1)(n'+2)}{n(n+1)(n+2)} p_q + \frac{1}{p_t}} = \frac{1}{p_x} = \frac{1}{u \cdot p_q + \frac{1}{p_t}}
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

□

Note that by suggested ergodicity, form of $n(n+1)(n+2)$ can be substituted any form of third order equation such as in $(n+X)(n+X+1)(n+X+2)$ such that $b \in \mathbb{N}_+$. And so, any integer has their regulated form in continued fractions with third order equation of prime number.

3 Uniqueness of continued fractions: finding glimpse of Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture

So the Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture will be proved if $2l \frac{n'(n'+1)(n'+2)}{n(n+1)(n+2)}$ constitutes uniqueness in continued fractions by any number given in relation to prime number. Then we can discuss Euler's continued fraction form[2].

$$a_0 + a_0 a_1 + \dots + a_0 a_1 a_2 \dots a_n = \frac{a_0}{1 - \frac{a_1}{1 + a_1 - \frac{a_2}{1 + a_2 - \frac{\ddots}{\ddots \frac{a_{n-1}}{1 + a_{n-1} - \frac{a_n}{1 + a_n}}}}} \tag{7}$$

Where the continued fraction forms finite sum. And by definition of Euler's continued fraction, uniqueness is assured in form when the a_n is a monotonic increasing sequence, which can be true in any prime number sequence.

Theorem 3.1. (Birch and Swinnerton-Dyer conjecture) Any given form of addition term in continued fraction constitutes the base in number of solutions in any form of integer derived problem.

Proof. Any solution from problem that ranges in rational number can be always constituted by sequential combinations of prime numbers, as stated in Euler's continued fraction. □

4 Application to ABC Conjecture

The problem of abc Conjecture can be defined as[3]:

Theorem 4.1. For relatively primes a, b, c

$$a + b = c \implies \begin{cases} \epsilon = 0 \text{ s.t. } \text{rad}(abc)^{1+\epsilon} < c \implies n(\{a, b, c\}) = \infty \\ \epsilon > 0 \text{ s.t. } \text{rad}(abc)^{1+\epsilon} < c \implies n(\{a, b, c\}) \neq \infty \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

Proof. Assuming for all the prime numbers that constitute a as $p_{a1}, p_{a2}, p_{a3} \cdots p_{an}$. And for b as $p_{b1}, p_{b2}, p_{b3} \cdots p_{bn}$, and for c as $p_{c1}, p_{c2}, p_{c3} \cdots p_{cn}$. For $rad(abc)$,

$$rad(abc) = rad(a)rad(b)rad(c) = rad(a)rad(b)rad(a+b) \quad (9)$$

This gives special condition of a , b , $a+b$ altogether being relatively prime. If so:

$$p_{a1}^x p_{a2}^y \cdots p_{an}^z + p_{b1}^q p_{b2}^r \cdots p_{bn}^s = p_{c1}^t p_{c2}^u \cdots p_{cn}^v \quad (10)$$

By expanding the equation given in prime number, any prime number larger than 2 can be claimed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} p_n &= z + M_1 p_a + M_2 p_b \cdots M_k p_m \text{ s.t. } M_k = k(k+1)(k+2), z \in \{0, 1, 3, 5\} \\ \implies p_n - z &= M_1 p_a + M_2 p_b \cdots M_k p_m \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

And note that any prime number takes following form in minimum:

$$p = n(n+1)(n+2)p' + p'' \quad (12)$$

If the p_{c1} ends in single term:

$$p_{a1}^x p_{a2}^y \cdots p_{an}^z + p_{b1}^q p_{b2}^r \cdots p_{bn}^s = p_{c1}^t \quad (13)$$

Assuming that p_{c1}^t takes form as $p_c - z (= M_1 p_\alpha + M_2 p_\beta \cdots M_k p_\gamma)$,

$$\begin{aligned} rad(abc) &= p_{a1} p_{a2} \cdots p_{an} p_{b1} p_{b2} \cdots p_{bn} p_{c1} \\ &= p_{a1} p_{a2} \cdots p_{an} p_{b1} p_{b2} \cdots p_{bn} rad(M_1 p_\alpha + M_2 p_\beta \cdots M_k p_\gamma + z) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

For all the cases in M_k :

$$\begin{cases} k=1 \Rightarrow 1 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 + (0 \text{ or } 1 \text{ or } 3 \text{ or } 5) \\ k=2 \Rightarrow 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 4 + (0 \text{ or } 1 \text{ or } 3 \text{ or } 5) \\ k=3 \Rightarrow 3 \cdot 4 \cdot 5 + (0 \text{ or } 1 \text{ or } 3 \text{ or } 5) \\ k=4 \Rightarrow 4 \cdot 5 \cdot 6 + (0 \text{ or } 1 \text{ or } 3 \text{ or } 5) \\ \dots \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

In every case, minimum division by number 2 or 3 can be provided. So, with the default claim of abc conjecture given in the first place:

$$\begin{aligned} rad(abc)^{1+\epsilon} &= ((2 \text{ or } 3 \leq) \cdot rad(abc'))^{1+\epsilon} \\ \implies \epsilon = 0 &\Rightarrow ((2 \text{ or } 3 \leq) \cdot rad(abc')) < c \Rightarrow n(c) = \infty \\ \implies \epsilon > 0 &\Rightarrow ((2 \text{ or } 3 \leq) \cdot rad(abc'))^{1+\epsilon} < c \Rightarrow n(c) \neq \infty \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Assuming that ϵ is 0, it directs infinite possible range of c by giving at minimum limit of 3 multiplication of rad . But ϵ gets bigger than 0, it arranges finite range of c by making growth by $rad(a)$ and $rad(b)$ more larger than 3 exponentially. Intuitively, this can be explained with relation to $(a+b)^{1+\epsilon} < (xa'b)^{1+\epsilon}$ when x is greater or equal than 3 and a can be divided by a' .

Example 4.1.1. In case of, $a=1, b=d^n-1, c=d^n, d \in \mathbb{N}_+$ ($\implies n(c) = \infty$ if $\epsilon = 0$), then $b(=d^n-1)$ always has prime factor that is equal or bigger than 3, so in any case of ϵ larger than 0 makes c restricted inevitably.

This can be understood with formerly given condition of continued fraction, also.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{p_x} &= \frac{1}{u \cdot p_q + \frac{1}{\frac{1}{p_t}}} \\ \implies \frac{1}{p_x p_y p_z \cdots} &= \frac{1}{u \cdot p_q + \frac{1}{\frac{1}{r \cdot p_s + \frac{1}{\frac{1}{p_v \cdots}}}}} \\ \text{s.t. } u \text{ or } r \cdots &\geq 2, p_x p_y p_z \cdots - p_q p_s \cdots < 0 \Rightarrow n(p_q, p_s \cdots) = \infty \\ \implies \frac{1}{p_x p_y p_z \cdots} &= \frac{1}{u^{1+\epsilon} \cdot p_q + \frac{1}{\frac{1}{r^{1+\epsilon} \cdot p_s + \frac{1}{\frac{1}{p_v \cdots}}}}} \\ \text{s.t. } u \text{ or } r \cdots &\geq 2 \text{ and } \epsilon > 0, p_x p_y p_z \cdots - p_q p_s \cdots < 0 \Rightarrow n(p_q, p_s \cdots) \neq \infty \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

□

5 Understanding relation to Hasse-Weil L-function

For here, we will discuss why modularity matters for Hasse-Weil L-function. Any modular equation defined as E_p by prime number p follows Hasse-Weil L-function as:

$$E_p : y^2 \equiv x^3 + Ax + B \pmod{p}$$

$$L(E, s) = \prod_p (1 - a_p p^{-s} + p^{1-2s})^{-1} \quad (18)$$

where $a_p = p + 1 - n(\{x|x \text{ being solution to } E_p\})$. For approaching the application, there can be three well-known cases to the modular operation.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Case 1.} \quad \text{Divider equals with the dividend} \Rightarrow p = x^3 + Ax + B \\ \text{Case 2.} \quad \text{Divider not equals but can divide the dividend} \\ \quad \quad \quad \text{without remainder} \Rightarrow p \neq x^3 + Ax + B, p \mid x^3 + Ax + B \\ \text{Case 3.} \quad \text{Divider not equals but can divide} \\ \quad \quad \quad \text{the dividend with remainder} \Rightarrow p \nmid x^3 + Ax + B \end{array} \right. \quad (19)$$

This classification has useful attribute derived by $x^2(Bx^{-2} + Ax^{-1} + x)$ and $x^3 - Cx^2 + Cx^2 + Ax + B$.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Case 1, 2.} \quad x^2(Bx^{-2} + Ax^{-1} + x) \\ \quad \quad \quad \Rightarrow x^2 \left(x - C' + A \left(x^{-1} + \frac{C'}{A} \right) + Bx^{-2} \right) \\ \quad \quad \quad \Rightarrow x^3 \left(1 - C' + Ax^{-1} \left(x^{-1} + \frac{C'}{A} \right) + Bx^{-3} \right) \\ \text{Case 3.} \quad x^3 - Cx^2 + Cx^2 + Ax + B \\ \quad \quad \quad \Rightarrow x^2(x - C) + Ax^2 \left(x^{-1} + \frac{C}{A} \right) + B \\ \quad \quad \quad \Rightarrow x(x^2 + A) + B \Rightarrow x^3(1 + Ax^{-2}) + B \end{array} \right. \quad (20)$$

These expansions can be applied in three cases of modular operation.

In case 1, modularity itself can be fostered by the innate equation repeatedly. This is case of continued fraction, which formerly visited. In case 2, equation in the whole terms can be divisible by any mean. And with case 1, 2, and 3, all the consequences by divisor follow the form repeatedly as given in L-function.

References

- [1] John Coates and Andrew Wiles. On the conjecture of birch and swinnerton-dyer. *Inventiones mathematicae*, 39(3):223–251, 1977.
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- [3] Joseph Oesterlé. Nouvelles approches du “théoreme” de fermat. *Astérisque*, 161(162):165–186, 1988.